

ARDC Institutional Underpinnings Phase 2 – Culture Element

1. Executive Summary

In 2021, the [ARDC](#) initiated a collaboration with 25 universities to develop a coordinated and collegially informed approach to research data management across Australia's universities by collaboratively developing and testing an institutional Research Data Management Framework (RDMF).

The RDMF is being designed to:

- Inform universities' design of policy, procedures, infrastructure and services
- Improve coordination of research data management within and between institutions
- Identify information needed for more efficient decision-making around retention and disposal of research data.

This report will break down eight of the elements of the RDMF currently under active consideration (figure A) and show the culture for each at Griffith by highlighting the ideal state vs the current state. The eighth element Culture, overlays across all others, as Culture plays such an integral part of our day-to-day activities:

- Active Data Management
- Data Management Planning
- Policy
- Retention and Disposal
- Sensitive Data
- Sharing, Publication and Open Research
- Support, Training and Guidance
- Culture

Figure A – Elements of the Research Data Management Framework showing culture encompassing and affecting all elements

A university-wide review was done to identify the culture of research data management. This review included structured interactions and Workshop. A Survey was sent to all academic staff and Interviews were conducted with nominated and self-nominated staff.

Overall, researchers genuinely value the importance in data management, but their experiences so far have been constrained by resources or are met with procedural speedbumps and roadblocks. As an organization, we can alleviate at least some of these constraints by [implementing the following changes](#).

From here, our next steps are to further investigate and implement these changes, and benchmark the change in culture after a time, post implementation. All of the proposed actions should lower a barrier, leading to a shift in culture to a more desired state. This will allow us to monitor the impact of the changes, track improvements and assess any further course correction needed. [\[Details\]](#)

1.1 Next steps

- Review findings from other institutions through outputs of the ARDC Institutional Underpinnings
- Summarise findings into key themes and meta-level issues.
- Formulate a roadmap to review and update proposed actions
- Link larger actions to Digital Master Plan and produce DIB proposals
- Re-run survey in two years to benchmark changes in current state, allowing us to assess changes in culture after implementing proposed actions.

2 Summary of proposed Actions

Element	Problems	Actions
<u>Culture</u>	Identified a disconnect between the aims of a researcher in their research data management and their experiences	The actions outlined in this document aim to align the experiences of researchers with their aims in research data management practices.
	There is no reward for researchers who practice good data management.	Rewards for good data practices can be reflected in incentives offered to researchers.
<u>Active Data Management</u>	Confusion over which 'approved' storage solution to use	A review of other university research storage infrastructure and learnings, to utilise learnings in assessing Griffith's current architecture for functionality.
<u>Data Management Planning</u>	Researchers are unsure what a data management plan looks like and have concerns around information security classification (data sensitivity) and where they can store their data. There is also ambiguity on data ownership and data transfer agreements.	Trigger actions for a Data Management Plan on new storage request. Offering a guide at an appropriate timepoint can help alter behaviour towards an ideal state.
	Data Management Plans are currently held as a MS Word document by individual researchers. Data Management Plans have limited re-useability Data management Plans are not considered living document	Discovery and Review of Data Management Plan Tools & Platforms.
	Data is needing to be retained for much longer than initially anticipated.	No Action required. Acknowledgement of a lack of available information when forecasting research storage costs to be funded.
	There is no clear role or responsibilities mapped, and no central overarching unit responsible for research data management. Referral pathways do exist, however, most are unofficial and via casual networking.	Clarify roles and responsibilities across the university on data management and establish clear referral pathways for research support groups.
<u>Retention and Disposal</u>	There is little/limited understanding of retention requirements.	Promotion of referral pathways for information on retention requirements via policy.

		Have a clear process to dispose of research data in an auditable/defensible way.
		Investigate how other universities are facilitating this archival process.
		Triggered notification at end of project with relevant project completion information.
<u>Sensitive Data</u>	Many researchers were unsure of exactly how to classify their data Many researchers also wanted more information in the cybersecurity and information security classification area.	Further upskilling around Data Storage, Sensitivity and Cybersecurity.
<u>Sharing, Publication and Open Research</u>	While researchers aim to publish their datasets as FAIR, leading to further citations and engagement, many are concerned about the accidental disclosure of sensitive data.	Investigate ways to provide clear methods to deidentify data, and further promote QCIF's Sensitive Data Consultations.
		Triggered notification at end of project with relevant project completion information to assist researchers to share their data via FAIR or Open publication where relevant.
	There is a low uptake on data transfer agreements, either formalised or informal. Data ownership is also not always clear across a project team.	Trigger actions on new storage requests for a Data management plan.
	There is a low understanding of General Data Protection Regulation and Defence Export Control.	Targeted educational material to researchers who have been flagged working with identified individuals or relevant disciplines.
	There is a potential misunderstanding or lack of clarity on data ownership between research groups.	Further educational material to all researchers (staff and students) on data ownership should be included as part of normal informational pathways.
<u>Support, Training and Guidance</u>	Training courses are offered and run by multiple departments at Griffith and researchers are not aware of all offerings.	Researcher-focused workshops should be listed in a single digital location (RED).
	Almost all interviewees stated they struggled to know who to talk to or where to go for certain topics, and in some cases were not even sure what questions to ask. Additionally, there was a lot of frustration about being stuck in support 'processes' without a human to talk to, for an extended amount of time.	Creation of a Data Management team.

	Both amongst researchers and research support staff, it was flagged that there was a lack of clarity around responsibility for Data Management.	<p>A decision on who has the ultimate responsibility for data management at Griffith University overall is needed</p> <p>Review outputs of the ARDC IU project from partner organisations for ideas and insights.</p>
Policy	As per the RISE workshop report, research support teams felt while there was sufficient coverage of policies, but more work was needed for the policy rules to be integrated into research systems.	<p>Promotion of referral pathways for information on retention requirements via policy</p> <p>Have a clear process to dispose of research data in an auditable/defensible way</p>

1.	Executive Summary	2
1.1	Next steps	3
2	Summary of proposed Actions	4
3	Introduction	9
3.1	Background	9
4	RDMF Elements.....	10
4.1	Culture	10
4.1.1	Scope of topic	10
4.1.2	Ideal State	10
4.1.3	Current state.....	10
4.1.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	11
4.2	Active Data Management.....	11
4.2.1	Scope of topic	11
4.2.2	Ideal State	12
4.2.3	Current state.....	12
4.2.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	15
4.3	Data Management Planning	15
4.3.1	Scope of Topic.....	15
4.3.2	Ideal State:	15
4.3.3	Current state:.....	15
4.3.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	19
4.4	Retention and Disposal.....	21
4.4.1	Scope of Topic.....	21
4.4.2	Ideal State:	21
4.4.3	Current state:.....	22
4.4.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	24
4.5	Sensitive Data	25
4.5.1	Scope of Topic.....	25
4.5.2	Ideal State:	25
4.5.3	Current state:.....	26
4.5.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	27
4.6	Sharing, Publication and Open Research.....	28
4.6.1	Scope of Topic.....	28

4.6.2	Ideal State:	28
4.6.3	Current state:	28
4.6.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	33
4.7	Support, Training and Guidance	34
4.7.1	Scope of Topic	34
4.7.2	Ideal State:	34
4.7.3	Current state	34
4.7.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	36
4.8	Policy	38
4.8.1	Scope of topic	38
4.8.2	Ideal State	38
4.8.3	Current state	38
4.8.4	Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State	38
5	Self-assessment benchmarking across Institutions	38
5.1	Summary of Results	38
6	Lessons learnt for future studies	38
7	Thanks	38
8	Appendix A - Methodology	39
9	Appendix B - Dictionary of Terms	39
10	Appendix C – ARDC RISE Report	40
11	Appendix D – Survey and Interview Details	40
12	Appendix E – Fantastic Researchers & Where to find them	41
13	Appendix F - Workshops currently offered across Griffith on Data Management	41
14	Appendix G – Case Studies of Data Management Consultant embedded into teams	41
15	Appendix H – Full details on qualitative responses	43
16	Appendix I – Survey Results Explorer	45
17	Appendix J – Scan of Open and FAIR published data from Griffith	45

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3 Introduction

3.1 Background

The ARDC Institutional Underpinnings (IU) project was split into two main phases:

Phase 1. Definition of the Framework

During 2021, the ARDC IU project:

- Identified eight key elements of the Research Data Management Framework (RDMF)
- Described the important challenges, considerations and opportunities of each element
- Gained broad acceptance of the RDMF elements' descriptions through consultation and feedback from participating institutions and external parties.

Phase 2. Implementation testing of the RDMF elements

During phase 2, each participating university was tasked with implementing the guidance given in the description of an element defined during phase 1. Implementation projects were guided by the following criteria set by the ARDC.

Implementations must:

1. Have ongoing value beyond the duration of the project
2. Involve improvement or change at your university (not just business-as-usual)
3. Specifically, test an aspect of the framework (i.e., help to evaluate the completeness/usefulness/correctness of guidance and resources provided)
4. Produce some output that can be of value to other institutions

For Phase 2, Griffith University chose to investigate the **culture of RDM** at Griffith, recognising that this aspect touches on all other elements of the RDMF and is central to effective RDM. The proposal for this implementation was to assess the current culture/attitude toward research data management against the recommendations tabled in Phase 1 Culture Change working group output.

This phase aimed to evaluate our current state and understand what the ideal state of RDM at Griffith would look like. The Phase 1 description of culture was summarised into three areas of activity:

- **Values** - What is important to the Individual (researcher) / Institution (university)
- **Aims** – What is the researcher/institution hoping to gain from this action?
- **Experiences** – How is the current state working? What can we alter/change to meet our aims and values?

The ideal RDM culture state was identified and described through:

- Workshops with RDM support staff at Griffith
- Analysis of current state documentation
- Consultation with other Universities

The current culture towards RDM at Griffith was identified and documented through:

- An RDM Survey was sent to all academic staff. – 170 respondents (~6% of researchers)

- 1:1 Interviews with nominated and volunteers – 20 participants (~0.6% of researchers)
- A self-evaluation against the Research Infrastructure Self Evaluation ([RISE](#)) Workshop
- Workshops with RDM support staff at Griffith
- Case studies of existing RDM

Further assessment of the ideal state will include reflection on the full ARDC IU report from all participating universities on all elements of the RDMF.

4 RDMF Elements

4.1 Culture

4.1.1 Scope of topic

Culture touches on all aspects of data management; thus, aspects of culture are covered not just in this element, but in all elements. Culture covers values, aims and experiences of both the individual researcher and the university overall. All other topics are viewed with a 'Culture' lens- how are the values, aims and experiences around each other element identified, measured in the current state and potentially improved by changes.

4.1.2 Ideal State

- The value of the researchers and the university would align
- The aims of the researchers and the university would align
- The experiences of researchers working towards these aims would be positive

4.1.3 Current state

Both researchers themselves and the university as a whole have aligned values and aims in data management.

Researchers referred to their data as their biggest asset, their 'bread and butter' and highlighted that good data management was its own reward. Many commented that ensuring your data was well maintained was part of being a responsible and ethical researcher.

However, there was a disconnect when it came to experiences in managing data.

Researchers talked about the time and opportunities lost while navigating different support processes or struggling to know where to go. Not knowing where to go for advice or even knowing what questions to ask was a distinct problem in itself.

Researchers were also struggling for time, knowing that the work they dedicated to data management would not be counted or valued in any promotional or funding outcomes, which made it hard to justify time away from other, more goal-weighted tasks.

Results for the survey question: At your current career level, what would be an incentive to reward you to have well-managed research data?

Figure 1- Incentives to have well managed data

4.1.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

Observed problem:

There is no reward for researchers who practice good data management.

Potential Action:

Rewards for good data practices can be reflected in incentives offered to researchers. A review of how this might best be achieved, with learnings gained from other universities participating in ARDC IU, would be beneficial.

Observed problem:

Researchers need more support and education in a timely manner on subjects, in a format that lessens the time cost associated with seeking support.

Potential Action:

The potential actions of this report should reflect a method that offers more support to researchers in a way that is a time improvement.

4.2 Active Data Management

4.2.1 Scope of topic

Active data management refers to the management of research data at any stage during the life of the project, including selection of what to collect/acquire, collection/acquisition, storage, analysis,

visualisation, and collaboration. Active data management ends when the data is either disposed of or moved to long-term storage after reporting is complete, Active data management does not include sharing data for re-use beyond the life of the original project.

4.2.2 Ideal State

In an ideal state, the following would be true:

- Researchers would be storing data in a Griffith-approved service according to the assigned information security classification
- Storage would be automatically allocated on project creation
- Backups of data would be automated and managed on approved Griffith solutions
- Stored data would be easily accessible to analysis tools
- Griffith storage infrastructure would contain functionality to monitor activity of datasets for potential archiving
- Griffith storage capacity would factor in future requirements

4.2.3 Current state

- While Research Space, Drive and Vault are promoted as the suggested location for research storage, an equal amount of people said they were using Research Storage locations such as SharePoint/Microsoft systems. OwnCloud/SharePoint and Research Space/Drive are both approved for data classified as Sensitive.
- For those who marked storing data 'on their own computers', most (65%) were retaining a copy on approved Griffith storage. 5% were storing data only on their computer while a further 12% were using only their own computers and an external hard drive as backup. *[Figure 3- Local copy backup location]*

Where researchers are storing their data:

What locations are you storing active research data?

Figure 2 - Locations of data storage

If you are keeping your data on your computer locally, where else is the data stored?

Figure 2- Local copy backup location

Approximately half of our researchers (49.6%) are storing at least 200GB of data for their current project
[Figure 4- Storage Size]

How much data do you store for your current project?

Figure 3- Storage Size

Over half (51.5%) of researchers are still manually backing up their data. [Figure 5 – Multiple Copies]

Of 22 interviewees, 4 mentioned too many storage options.

Do you have multiple copies of your data?

Figure 4- Multiple Copies

4.2.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

Observed problem:

There are multiple 'Griffith Approved' storage infrastructure options, all segregated from one another and each with their benefits and limitations. Some researchers found it confusing to have multiple options available, meaning they might not be able to select an ideal system for their workflows.

Proposed Action:

A review of other university research storage infrastructure and learnings, to utilise learnings in assessing Griffith's current architecture for functionality. This will lower the existing barrier, leading to a desired cultural shift.

4.3 Data Management Planning

4.3.1 Scope of Topic

Data Management Planning incorporates all preparation activities prior to starting a project. This can include establishing data needs prior to applying for grants, creating a Data Management Plan to act as a Standard Operating Protocol for the team and preparing legal/regulatory agreements.

4.3.2 Ideal State:

- All research projects would have a Data Management Plan in place, shared with all project members and updated during the project lifetime as a living document.
- Metadata about a research project is entered into a central system once, as semi-structure/structured data and shared with other appropriate systems.
- Triggers from the data management system should proactively connect researchers with research support groups and other related services.
- Researchers would find benefit in the time taken to complete a Data Management Plan
- Researchers would know how much data they would need to collect at grant application stage
- Griffith University would have a clear forecast of how much research data needed to be stored per annum.
- Data Management Plans would be used for infrastructure capacity planning e.g., Storage and Application Support (Survey Tools) etc.
- Across Griffith, all researchers and research support staff would have a clear understanding of who 'leads' data management planning and the scope of involvement for each support group.

4.3.3 Current state:

- Library maintains a guide on Data Management Plans and provides Microsoft Word templates for researchers to use.
- Data management plans are sent to relevant grant winners in a Word document form. Post-Award team (Office of Research) retain a copy of this initial Data Management Plan.
- Data Management plans submitted to Post-Award team (Office of Research) are reviewed by eResearch (Digital Solutions).
- Not all researchers have a data management plan in place.

Data Storage forecasting is based on the annual organic growth percentage of 20%. Unfortunately, this organic growth does not account for ingress of new research groups into the university, who may bring

across datasets with large storage needs.

Data Management Plans

Do you have a Data Management Plan in Place?

Figure 5- Data Management Plan

Only 34% of respondents said they had a written Data Management Plan (DMP) in place (formal or informal), while 23% stated they had a 'verbal' data management plan. 35% said they were not familiar with Data Management plans. [As per Figure 6 above]

Why does your team have a data management plan in place?

Figure 6- Why have a Data Management Plan?

Many researchers (34 responses) who have a data management plan have done so following a request from an internal Griffith Research Support team, or to meet internal organisation/auditing needs (29 responses). [Above: Figure 7 – Why have a Data Management Plan]

When queried on why they did not have a Data Management Plan, the most popular reason was a lack of understanding of what a DMP should look like, which indicates a need for more awareness of the

DMP guides and the need to have a plan in the first place. ["Why do you not have a data management plan in place?"] ["Why do you not have a data management plan in place?"]

For those that are already using Data Management Plans, 60% were updating their plans over time. ["Do you update your DMP?"].

What benefits do you gain from completing a Data Management Plan?

Figure 7- Benefits gained

Additionally, many stated the benefits received from a DMP was "Ability to share with team members" (54 responses), "Reproducibility" (35 responses), "Assists with Auditing" (28 responses) with only a small number of people completing "Due to Compliance Reasons" (9) [Above: Figure 8 - Benefits gained]. This offers potential benefits to be highlighted to researchers who are unsure about the benefits of DMPs.

Research storage forecasting

At what stage of your project would you know how much data you will create/need to store?

Figure 8- Projected Data Creation of a Project

Few researchers (13%) knew when applying for grants how much data storage they would need for the duration of that project, making it difficult to include storage costs into grants (where grants allow infrastructure costs to be included). Most researchers (70%) were not able to forecast how much data storage they would need until either data was being gathered or until the end of project. [Figure 9 – Projected Data Creation of a Project].

What percentage of data on your current project is from your/your team's previous projects?

Figure 9- Data reuse

Almost half of researchers reused previous project data, which has a major effect on retention periods. Along with other implications, it means that research storage is not being released at the end of a project. [Figure 10 – Data Reuse].

In the past year, did you delete any data no longer needed?

Figure 10- data deletion

Additionally, many researchers (64%) are never deleting data. [Figure 11– data deletion]

4.3.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

Observed problem:

Researchers are unsure what a data management plan looks like and have concerns around information security classification (data sensitivity) and where they can store their data. There is also ambiguity on data ownership and data transfer agreements. Offering a guide at an appropriate timepoint can help alter behaviour towards an ideal state.

Potential Action:

- Trigger actions for a Data Management Plan on new storage request

Example: When a researcher requests new storage, an email is sent back to them, highlighting a guide on Data Management Plans and where they can seek help. There is also potential to add further information such as how to learn about Information Security Classification (data sensitivity) and how that affects their processes and the actions they need to take to adequately protect the

data/information. A reminder to discuss with the research team on data ownership and the Data Transfer Agreement template can also be included, with links to support for both.

Observed problem:

Data Management Plans are currently held as a Word template by individual researchers. This limits the ability to trigger actions at certain project milestones that provides researchers with time-relevant information, saving the researcher time to seek information themselves.

This also means researchers are spending time supplying information at multiple locations instead of being able to spend time on the tasks that progress and add value to their research.

This also limits the information gathered about researcher behaviours, which can hinder the potential actions the university might choose to take towards the overall university aims.

Potential Action:

- **Discovery and Review of Data Management Plan Tools and Platforms**

Many universities are leveraging data management software which offers researchers an online platform where they can build an online Data Management Plan. As they build a plan, automated triggers set researchers up with relevant internal systems (Storage, survey or microscopy access, eLabNotebook, information about sensitive data etc).

This review should focus on integrations with current and upcoming Griffith platforms and providing researchers with a clear idea of what platforms they and their team have accounts and data on. Any solutions should aim to save researchers time, instead of being another process to follow.

Many universities have Data Management Platforms in place that Griffith could use as an example to learn and build on.

While the current Data Management Plan templates are a good step towards the ideal, a more automated system would save researchers time, assist with reproducibility by providing a shared knowledge space of data locations, as well as providing the added benefit of recording statistics on researcher behaviours and monitoring for emerging compliance and regulatory obligations.

Observed problem:

As many researchers are reusing subsets of data previously created by their project team for further research, data is needing to be retained for much longer than initially anticipated. Compounding this is the lack of information on how much data is destined for ingest into research storage until storage is needed. This inability to predict the upcoming behaviour of researchers hampers forecasting for research storage. While not captured in this study, the influx of data from key researchers incoming to Griffith affects predictions of storage forecasts, as often key researchers travel with large amounts of data.

Potential Action:

- **No Action, Acknowledgement of a lack of available information when forecasting research storage costs to be funded**

As an informational piece, when reviewing funding of Research Storage, there should be an acknowledgement that researchers themselves are unaware of how much storage would be needed, or how much they will be able to release back into the system, both of which affect the ability to forecast storage costs going into the future.

Observed Problem:

While various support groups around the university handle subsets of data management, there is no clear role or responsibilities mapped, and no central overarching unit responsible. Referral pathways do exist, however, most are unofficial and via casual networking.

Potential Action:

- **Clarify roles and responsibilities across the university on data management and establish clear referral pathways for research support groups.**

4.4 Retention and Disposal

4.4.1 Scope of Topic

Research data is an immense, diverse and valuable resource that requires specific management by researchers and institutions over extended periods of time. This is particularly evident once a research project's active phase has been completed, when long-term plans for data storage, retention and disposal need to be implemented, and the responsibility for on-going management of data is passed to different stakeholders and administrators. We recognise that the storage, retention and disposal of research data require specific management actions that take place often many years after the research project has been completed, so processes need to be developed that ensure that the information needed to drive future management decisions and processes is carried forward. These processes are integral to reining in burgeoning storage costs, and meeting legislative requirements and appropriate treatment of data post-project.

4.4.2 Ideal State:

- An institute would have a clear idea of research datasets which includes the likely retention periods, with an automated trigger to suggest recorded deletion post-retention date.
- Researchers would have a clear pathway for determining retention requirements
- Data no longer needed would be retained for the required time, then prompted for deletion with a defensible disposition process in place.

4.4.3 Current state:

What percentage of data on your current project is from your/your team's previous projects?

Figure 11- Reuse of Project team data

Almost half of researchers reuse previous project data, having a major effect on retention periods. [Figure 12 – Reuse of Project team data]. Along with other implications, it means that research storage is not being released at the end of a project. Additionally, as below, many researchers (64%) are never deleting data at all. [Figure 11 – data deletion].

This means that for a dataset, the retention period is constantly being reset depending on its reuse. It also suggests that there are potentially datasets being kept longer than the required minimum retention period. Data was deleted for a range of reasons.

Data deletion is also not occurring in coordination with Information Management. A defensible disposal process is one where there is sufficient metadata retained to:

- Describe the information/data/records being deleted
- The authorised record class under which it is being deleted
- The date it was due for destruction
- The date it was destroyed
- Authorisation of the disposal

The above metadata is required to be retained for 50 years.

For data you have deleted in the past year, was it:

Figure 12- Nature of deleted data

Researchers were largely unaware of where to go to learn about retention requirements, with 72.5% answering "No" to "Do you know where to go to learn about retention periods?". Researchers went to the following locations to learn about retention times:

Figure 13- Where researchers go to learn about retention times

4.4.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

Observed Problem:

There is little/limited understanding of retention requirements. Researchers are not deleting their data, potentially violating their ethics agreements and tying up research storage capacity. Offering a behavioural trigger to facilitate archiving of data with a specified retention period, and assistance to publish data where appropriate could alleviate this.

Potential Action:

- **Promotion of referral pathways for information on retention requirements via policy**

Further promotion of the "Schedule of Retention Periods for Research Data and Primary Material" policy in the Griffith Policy library as the authoritative source is needed. An audit of existing support materials to ensure information reflects the current policy.

- **Have a clear process to dispose of research data in an auditable/defensible way**

Review of the 'Schedule for Retention Periods for Research Data' policy, to include how to dispose of research data in an auditable way.

- **Investigate how other universities are facilitating this archival process.**
- **Triggered notification at end of project with relevant project completion information**

Example: A trigger email to researchers offering assistance in archiving their data with retention requirements included and information about publishing their data in a FAIR or Open format. This could be assisted by the suggested "Data Management" team. This trigger could be the completion email upon receipt of a final ethics report (which covers many but not all research), at a certain point in a HDR candidature milestone, and/or a time (potentially 3 years) post-creation of a storage account.

Previously mentioned - **Acknowledgement of a lack of available information when forecasting research storage costs to be funded** due to rolling retention periods and data not being deleted when expected.

4.5 Sensitive Data

4.5.1 Scope of Topic

"Sensitive data" can be difficult to define, making it hard to have meaningful discussions about how to manage sensitive research data. We can identify classes of data that are definitely sensitive - for instance, individual patient records, information about the nesting location of an endangered species of bird, or test results that reveal the most effective way to produce a microorganism that could be used as a bioweapon. However, it is harder to agree upon the properties that cause all of these types of data to be grouped into the category "sensitive". In order to sensibly address this area, it is helpful to consider our aims when discussing RDM for sensitive data.

For the purposes of institutional research data management, all of the types of sensitive data discussed above are united by the need for special protections and controls to be put in place around their management, including the collection, storage, access and sharing of those data. Universities are motivated to address the sensitivity of data in order to ensure compliance with ethical and regulatory requirements and manage risk. Data can pose many kinds of risk if mishandled or exposed (including risk to individuals, risk to environments, risk to corporate interests, risk to national security, and legal and reputational risk to the university itself).

4.5.2 Ideal State:

- Researchers would have a good understanding of how sensitive their data is, and how that relates to storage options (repositories), geographic or other compliance limitations (e.g, can't stored offshore) and analysis options (approved tools commensurate to the sensitivity).
- Researchers would know where to go to find out about Information Security Classification (data sensitivity).
- All hard drives used would be encrypted for security.
- Researchers would feel confident in how to securely share their sensitive data.
- Researchers would feel confident when they release their data in a FAIR or Open way, that the data will not have any sensitive data concerns.

- Researchers would feel confident deidentifying their data and appropriately supported.

4.5.3 Current state:

- 11 comments across 22 interviewees stated they were unsure on data security or wanted more guidance on cybersecurity requirements
- 45 people attended sensitive data training in 2021
- QCIF offers an one hour free consultation to review deidentification of a dataset to ensure no accidental disclosures.

For your current project, Do you know your information security classification (how sensitive your data is) ?

Figure 14- Security knowledge

One third of participants knew that their data was not open and should be treated carefully, however they were not aware of any specific requirements. Additionally, another 19% were not sure of their information security classification. [Figure 15- Security knowledge]

It was also noted that the research support teams as part of this project felt that the % of respondents to "Yes, it was protected" was surprisingly high given their knowledge of data assets at Griffith.

Do you know who to ask at Griffith to determine how safe/cybersecure an external company/online platform is?

Figure 15- Where to seek support on Cybersecurity

As [per Appendix H](#), 54 respondents stated "No" to knowing how to find out if an online platform was considered safe to use. [Figure 16- Where to seek support on Cybersecurity]

4.5.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

Observed Problem:

Many researchers were unsure of exactly how to classify their data for sensitivity, meaning their behaviour may not necessarily reflect the need to adequately protect the data. Many researchers also wanted more information in the cybersecurity and information security classification area.

Potential Actions:

- **Further upskilling around Data Storage, Sensitivity and Cybersecurity**

Example: This workshop would focus on the different data storage options, how to assess the Information Security Classification (data sensitivity) of their data and how that affects where the data can be stored and used. This can also cover how IT systems are classified from a cybersecurity

perspective and some considerations for researchers wanting to use external IT platforms to be aware of.

4.6 Sharing, Publication and Open Research

4.6.1 Scope of Topic

Open research comprises not just access to publications and data sharing that is 'as open as possible, [only] as closed as necessary', but also documentation of data (metadata, e.g., record-, dataset-, Instrument- and project-level metadata; administrative metadata; data provenance including version history) and research processes ('paradata', e.g., data capture and processing techniques and methods, software, notebooks, samples), sufficient to allow the assessment, testing, and reproduction of research results.

4.6.2 Ideal State:

- All data where possible would be published as Open or [FAIR](#) data.
- Researchers would have a good understanding of Open and FAIR.
- Datasets and Publication would be promoted via GRO to encourage citations and reuse.
- Statistics on reused datasets would be collated for university review.
- All datasets would be licensed and ethically allowed to be shared where possible.
- Researchers would be assured that the datasets published did not contain any sensitive data.
- Griffith University would have suggested locations and workflows for Open and FAIR data
- Storage solutions provided would enable collaborative work, whether collaborators were external, university-affiliated, or other.
- All members of the research team, including HDR students, have a clear understanding of who owns individual datasets (separate to custodianship).

4.6.3 Current state:

- There is currently a 'Considerations for sharing research data' guide being created for researchers.
- Initial scan found at minimum 250+ Griffith affiliated datasets published as Open or FAIR across external repositories [[Appendix J – 1](#)].
- QCIF offers one hour free consults to review datasets prior to publication to verify no accidental data disclosure would occur, with <5 researchers utilising this service.

Do you share data with external parties?

Figure 16- Sharing Externally

There are a larger proportion of researchers that share data with external parties (96 responses) versus not sharing data externally (78 responses). [Figure 17 - Sharing Externally] [Counts as [per Appendix H](#)]

Given the explanation of FAIR, would you:

Figure 17- Thoughts on FAIR

Researchers are interested in sharing their data as [FAIR](#), but have not yet taken the step. [Figure - Thoughts on FAIR] [Counts as [per Appendix H](#)]. One of the major blockers to publishing as FAIR is the concerns about accidental disclosure of sensitive data, with 21 responses. [Figure 20- Blockers to FAIR publication]. Few researchers (<5) are currently utilising the QCIF sensitive data consults.

What would stop you sharing your data in a FAIR way?

Figure 18- Blockers to FAIR publication

Do you have a collaboration agreement of some description (formal or informal) with your external collaborators?

Figure 19- Collaboration Agreement

Almost half of researchers said they do not have an informal or formal collaborative agreement with external collaborators.

Does everyone in your research project have a shared understanding on who owns the data?

Figure 20- Ownership understanding

From the survey results, most respondents (78%) said there was a shared understanding of ownership across the team. [Figure 22 – Ownership understanding]. However, during interviews, responses for the question "Do you and everyone in your research project have a shared understanding on who owns the data?" revealed a lot of variation. Only 4 respondents felt confident that this was clear in their groups, due to the nature of their data and contracts or agreements made. Some (3) responded that data ownership became difficult working with collaborators or Indigenous groups because of Griffith's policies around ownership. Another 5 respondents stated ownership was "Half understood" in their groups and 4 respondents stated there was no understanding in their groups on ownership. [\[As per appendix H\]](#)

The interviewer was also surprised by the number of researchers who stated that the academic owned the data, despite the general policy of Griffith University owning all data unless another arrangement was made, however the interviewer was not in the position to verify specific assertions on ownership.

Only 23.3% of researchers were aware of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and only 18.2% were aware of the Defence Export Control requirements. As any researcher working with identified data should be aware of the General Data Protection Regulation, and Defence Export Control (DEC) can affect researchers especially in the STEM fields, this shows a lot more risk management education in this space is needed.

Information is included in the Griffith University Research Ethics Manual [Booklet 23 "Privacy"] on GDPR and DEC. There is currently a review of Griffith University's Privacy Plan, scheduled for August.

4.6.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

Observed Problem:

While researchers aim to publish their datasets as FAIR, leading to further citations and engagement, many are concerned about the accidental disclosure of sensitive data.

Potential Actions:

- **Investigate ways to provide clear methods to deidentify data, and further promote QCIF's Sensitive Data Consultations**

QCIF currently offers one-hour free consultations to review a dataset prior to publication to safeguard against accidental disclosure of sensitive data. More promotion of this service is needed. Additionally, further highlighting of 'How to deidentify sensitive data' guides available.

- Previously mentioned - **Triggered notification at end of project with relevant project completion information** to assist researchers to share their data via FAIR or Open publication where relevant.

Example: Further promotion of the 'Considerations for sharing research data' page currently in development when researchers are sent a trigger notification at the end of a project.

Observed Problem:

There is a low uptake on data transfer agreements, either formalised or informal. Data ownership is also not always clear across a project team. Offering a trigger to change behaviour and start conversations is important.

Potential Action:

- **Trigger actions on new storage request for a Data management plan**

Include a link to the Data Transfer Agreement template and where to seek assistance during a new storage request process.

Observed Problem:

There is a low understanding of General Data Protection Regulation and Defence Export Control.

Potential Action:

- **Targeted educational material to researchers who have been flagged working with identified individuals or relevant disciplines**

Example – Via the ethics process, if a researcher flags that they are working with identified individuals, some existing educational material should be automatically emailed to the researcher with relevant information around General Data Protection Regulation.

Observed Problem:

There is a potential misunderstanding or lack of clarity on data ownership between research groups.

Potential Action:

- **Further educational material to all researchers (staff and students) on data ownership should be included as part of normal informational pathways.**

Example:

As part of the research school seminars, a short presentation on data ownership would be hosted, outlining at a high level what potential obstacles could occur and identifying the referral pathway for more support. It is highly encouraged that senior academics/leaders attend, to lead the culture change from the top down.

4.7 Support, Training and Guidance

4.7.1 Scope of Topic

Researchers cannot be expected to know how to manage data effectively without support, training, and guidance as data management is complex, institutionally and discipline-specific and multifaceted. Support, training, and guidance is the vector by which all other elements of the Institutional Underpinnings framework are delivered to/enabled for researchers. For example: knowledge gained through education, combined with skills acquired through training is a key component of culture change; researchers performing data management planning will require guidance on how to go through the process and what must be done with the plan; appropriate cybersecurity approaches must be communicated through advice and assisted support.

Universities can ensure researchers are equipped with the knowledge and skills to comply with national and university research data management requirements by committing to provide foundational education and skills in RDM through the provision of support, training and guidance to their researchers. This enables researchers to conduct research effectively and ethically.

4.7.2 Ideal State:

- All training should be highly accessible and linked to appropriate support documentation.
- The benefit to researchers to undertake training is clear and incentivising.
- All training is easy to find, and potentially offered as self-paced modules to assist researchers at point of need.
- Training should be seen as a continuum and not a one-off.
- Training for HDR students and new staff should be provided at the appropriate time, and self-paced modules offered as additional training support.
- There should be clarity around obligations for researchers under the *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research*.

4.7.3 Current state

- Of 22 interviewees
 - o there were 7 mentions where information was hard to find.

- 3 mentions where “Clarity of Responsibility was needed” internal to academic departments.
- 3 mentions of “Too much Process” while seeking help.
- There were 13 mentions where researchers requested access to a data management professional or team.
- Positive experience via direct help from a person was mentioned 4 times.
- A number of researchers stated that they paid money to solve an issue that could not be solved following the support process.
 - Two researchers stated they could not print with MacOS, meaning one research group purchased printers.
 - One research group stated they spent six months trying to get an external-facing informational website before eventually giving up and making one themselves. This website now brings in external collaborators and external funding to the team, but the team missed out on six months of external funding while trying to navigate the process.
- Two research groups hired a data manager to assist their lab groups with organising and maintaining their data. Their experiences were very positive and having a dedicated data management professional added significant value to the projects and teams. Reference to case studies in [Appendix G](#).
- Recently Office for Research has published a New Researcher Induction Guide in May 2022.
- Obligations under the *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research* are covered in consultations and written guides.

Where do researchers go for training?

Figure 21- Where to seek training

Research Education and Development (RED) training was mentioned the most, with 53 mentions of the 308 locations suggested. Groups such as Library, Hacky Hours and eResearch Services were mentioned separately but all of them run their workshops through RED as well. [\[Link to full table in Appendix H\]](#)

RED ran 224 workshops in 2021.

Additionally, many researchers expect information about upcoming training to arrive in their inboxes, highlighting that email is their preferred method to hear about upcoming training.

4.7.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

Observed Problem:

Training courses are offered and run by multiple departments at Griffith and researchers are not aware of all offerings.

Potential Actions:

- **Researcher focused workshops should be listed in a single digital location (RED)**

Example: Many researchers already default to the RED team to find workshops. While many researcher-focused workshop providers have organically moved to RED to coordinate and deliver their workshops, a default stance for RED to run all researcher-related workshops would be beneficial.

It also has the advantage of ensuring training dates do not overlap and providing researchers with a “one-stop shop” for training.

This would move a considerable administrative load to the Research Education and Development team, alleviating the burden on educators. Additional funding would be required to expand the RED team’s capacity.

Due to automation implemented in RED workflows, the amount of work it takes to establish a workshop through RED would be less than each individual educator maintaining their own bookings.

Observed Problem:

Almost all interviewees stated they struggled to know who to talk to or where to go for certain topics, and in some cases were not even sure what questions to ask. Additionally, there was a lot of frustration about being stuck in support ‘processes’ without a human to talk to, for an extended amount of time. Feedback once a human was there to help was overwhelmingly positive. There were multiple instances where being stuck in support processes meant projects failed, extra costs were incurred, or financial opportunities were being missed.

Potential Action:

- **Creation of a Data Management team**

Establish a new team of research support staff embedded into Schools to help guide better data management, highlighting concerns that researchers may not know to ask about.

In two individual cases (documented in Appendix G) research groups at Griffith hired a data management consultant. These consultants worked across the project team to build Standard Operating Procedures with external collaborators at Qld Health, helped build Data Management Plans, acted as a referral point for researchers, ensured data was organised and archived (including when researchers left the team). In both cases, this was seen as a valuable role that saved researchers time, money and reputation loss.

Macquarie University implemented this with fantastic feedback from researchers (but did not continue due to COVID-inspired budgetary cuts). Further investigation is needed into other universities that offered this service to understand and analyse the benefits.

This group could also assist in highlighting bottlenecks in processes, and providing insight into potential resolutions of bottlenecks.

Observed Problem:

Both amongst researchers and research support staff, it was flagged that there was a lack of clarity around responsibility for Data Management.

Potential Action:

- A decision on who has the ultimate responsibility for data management at Griffith University overall is needed.
- Review outputs of ARDC IU project from partner organisations for ideas and insights.

4.8 Policy

4.8.1 Scope of topic

Policy covers specific rules regarding research data. In the Griffith context, all policy is represented under the Policy library. For the context of this report, policy has been discussed in conjunction with other elements above where relevant.

4.8.2 Ideal State

Policy would reflect and support the institution's research strategy.

4.8.3 Current state

Research data management policy is covered in The Responsible Conduct of Research Policy.

4.8.4 Detailed Actions to move towards Ideal State

As per the RISE workshop report, research support teams felt while there was sufficient coverage of policies, but more work was needed for the policy rules to be integrated into research systems.

Previously mentioned - **Promotion of referral pathways for information on retention requirements via policy**

Previously mentioned - **Have a clear process to dispose of research data in an auditable/defensible way**

5 Lessons learnt for future studies

The ARDC RISE workshop was run after we had already finalised the Culture Survey questions.

We suggest for other universities wanting to run a similar review, to undertake the ARDC RISE program prior to writing survey questions as we found a few questions that we would have like to add or change during this time.

6 Thanks

Thank you to all researchers who took the time to share their feedback in the surveys and interviews.

Thank you to all the research support teams who took time to share their thoughts, feedback and ideas on Current state, Ideal state and more.

Thank you to all parties involved in bringing this report together. Many hours of work were involved and all groups were incredibly supportive and dedicated to bringing these statistics, insights and actions together.

Thank you to Denise Treacher, who shared insights and lessons learnt from Macquarie University's work in this space, as well as sharing their interview questions.

Thank you to ARDC for bringing together 25 universities and leading the wider project, and all participants of the ARDC Institutional Underpinnings project for their contributions, previous and ongoing, that led to this report.

7 Appendix A - Methodology

Who was asked to complete the survey?

- All active academics were invited to participate in the survey.
- All active higher degree candidates were invited to participate in the survey

Surveys that were partially complete were still included in the analysis, as most questions were not reliant on previous questions.

Other than demographics, all questions were optional. Not all participants responded to all questions.

Why we chose this audience:

- Adjunct academics were included as researchers who would likely be working across institutes.
- Emeritus academics were included as researchers with long term experience in the Griffith ecosystem.
- On consultation, almost all academics were both researching and teaching, or had performed research previously.

Please also see [Appendix E “Fantastic Researchers and where to find them”](#) regarding how the mailing lists for this group was sourced.

Who was asked to complete the interviews?

- All active academics and higher degree candidates who completed the survey were offered an interview to expand on their views.
- Invitations were also sent out to key researchers nominated by the project board.

How questions were built:

- Different areas of the Phase 1 project.
- Research support groups were invited to suggest questions.
- Questions were also inspired by previous benchmarking scans done by other universities.

How qualitative data was analysed:

Using a thematic based analysis with NVivo software. Themes were highlighted in interviews and open text questions to find common topics with associated sentiments and roadblocks.

8 Appendix B - Dictionary of Terms

Term or Terms known by	Description
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons - https://ardc.edu.au/about_us/ As a national research infrastructure provider, the ARDC facilitates partnerships to develop a coherent research environment that enables researchers to find, access, contribute to and effectively use services to maximise research quality and impact.

Academics	All staff members with an academic category as part of their HR profile.
Active Research Data	Data that is used to derive research outcomes – includes raw data, working data and final results.
HDR Candidates	Higher Degree Research Candidates – Research students
Information Security Classification	A classification scheme which categorises how sensitive a dataset is and the protections needed at that classification.
The institute	Griffith University as a whole institute
DMP	Data Management Plan – a template provided to researchers to assist them in planning their incoming datasets for that specific project.
RED	Research Education and Development team
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation as per https://www.oaic.gov.au/privacy/guidance-and-advice/australian-entities-and-the-eu-general-data-protection-regulation
Defence Export Controls	As per https://www.defence.gov.au/business-industry/export/controls
Research Support groups	Groups such as Office of Research, Griffith Library, Digital Solutions, Griffith Legal, Griffith Graduate Research School and all other teams that assist researchers
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reuseable; As per https://ardc.edu.au/resources/aboutdata/fair-data/#:~:text=FAIR%20provides%20a%20useful%20framework,sharing%20and%20reuse%20of%20data . This is a way to publicly share the metadata of your dataset, and invite other researchers to request the dataset itself without making the data open to the public. Gateways can be included prior to the data being released such as acknowledgement of Indigenous restrictions etc.
RISE	Research Infrastructure Self Evaluation (RISE) mode

9 Appendix C – ARDC RISE Report

RISE Report results kept internally at Griffith University.

10 Appendix D – Survey and Interview Details

Questions asked during interviews:

- Could you tell us about your current research projects? And how you manage your data?
- If you have external collaborators, do the current data storage solutions still meet your need?
- What are some of the problems that you encountered using technology that Griffith supplies for research?
- In the last year what have you spent money (department, grant or personal money) to solve technology problems?
- Are there training gaps that you can see in the space of DM?
- Are there support gaps that you can see in the space of DM?
- What is the one thing that would make a big difference to your data management?

- Do you receive conflicting advice from different parts of the university on Data Management? If so, where?
- At your career level (which is?), what reward or bonus would be an incentive for you?
- Do you and everyone in your research project have a shared understanding on who owns the data?
- Have you ever completed a DMP?
- What do you think about the current DMP process?
- Would you like to add anything else?

11 Appendix E – Fantastic Researchers & Where to find them

The Ironic Story of Researcher Metadata

One of the challenges we met while sending out the survey is finding a mailing list that included all researchers. While there was a tag in the HR Peoplesoft system for higher degree research students, there was no equivalent group in any identity system identifying a staff member as a researcher.

While many individual Research Support Groups had their own mailing lists, these were discounted for use so as not to introduce bias. In the end, the survey was sent out to all staff marked as academics.

12 Appendix F - Workshops currently offered across Griffith on Data Management

RED workshop	Number of sessions (Mar 2021 – Apr 2022)	Total attendees across all sessions
Managing your research data	3	106
External research datasets	4	92
Reproducible research	3	62
Working with sensitive data	2	45

13 Appendix G – Case Studies of Data Management Consultant embedded into teams

Case Study

- Interviews dates: discussion with two staff members took place on 25th May 2022 and 14th June 2022.
- Role's duration: from 2010 to 2016 and in 2020 for a year.
- Tasks performed:
 - First point of contact for main Q&As - a go-to person to direct researchers on what to do and where to go.
 - Create, maintain and update the Data Management System, guidelines and protocol around data management internally and externally.
 - Migrate existing projects according to existing protocols and compliance.

- Perform regular checks and internal audit – compliance based on Griffith and external collaborators.
 - Develop content and deliver workshops related to data management risks, excellent attendance (early career researchers, high attendance).
 - Coordinate handover tasks, ensure data is saved when a staff member leaves.
 - Onboard, induct new team members into the process and protocols.
 - Assist with “panic” emails – ethics and submission deadlines, the form, process, project closure checklist.
 - Educate users using contextualised scenarios, highlighting issues and consequences.
 - Create the Data Management System guidelines and protocol around Data Management.
 - Assist with the use of the Data Classification Tool – self-help (GU tool) – ranks data – often directed users to it Ethics, Governance, Library.
 - Ad hoc requests such as helping with completing the DM Plan, file structure.
- ◆ Benefits of having a dedicated DM role:
- People can be taught the very real risks of not having and updating a Data Management Plan.
 - A dedicated role would save key researchers’ time, for example, not having a cycle of documentation being rejected as sub-standard and/or requiring re-submission.
 - Data management is an evolving "beast" - constant changes need to be implemented and communicated.
 - Support resources are overstretched – a suggestion that came up was to have a dedicated channel and self-help tool for data management information, as well as a dedicated hotline.
 - Early career researchers – such a big task for them, particularly if they are new to GU – not part of the onboarding process, the responsibility falls under the team – a legacy of misinformation, high level Professors are not sure about the correct protocols – this cascades through.
 - Data management best practices should be part of the onboarding module, for example, and training should be refreshed on an ongoing basis.
 - This would bring Griffith in line with RDM practices at peer universities such as UQ and QUT.
- ◆ Skills required in a DM role:
- Research knowledge/background, ethics, governance, data management in a research capacity.
 - Experience working with documentation, tech-savvy, following policies/procedures
 - Experience in research data and tools used in research that involves storage, data gathering, data analysis and surveys.
 - Strong interpersonal and negotiation skills, problem-solving, flexibility, proactivity.
 - Ethics and grants applications, early career researchers could suit the role.
 - Strong Microsoft Office, Sway skills.
 - Extensive knowledge of both Griffith University systems and requirements.
 - Background in ethics/governance/data management and/or a good understanding of the national legislation and state frameworks .
 - Someone with a background in research ideally.

→ Needs to be patient, organised, and with strong attention to detail.

14 Appendix H – Full details on qualitative responses

These responses were open text fields or interview question responses, coded via the NVIVO system.

Do you know who to ask at Griffith to determine how safe/cybersecure an external company/online platform is?

	Responses
No	54
Yes (No desc)	12
Digital Solutions	8
eResearch	8
Cybersecurity	6
Ethics	2
Office of Research	2
Supervisor	1

Where would you go to discover training at Griffith University?

	Responses
Research Education and Devel	53
Webpage search (Griffith main page or Google)	26
Emails (All)	13
School Emails	9
GGRS	9
Library	8
Blackboard	8
Supervisor	7
Learning Futures	5
eResearch	3
I don't know where to go	3
Talk to Peers	2
Hacky Hours	2
IT Services	2
GUPSA	1
Ask Element-based Research Officer	1
Staff Portal	1

GIFT	1
Ethics	1
Office of Research	1
Human Resources	1
GURMA (Griffith Uni Research Methodology Advisors)	1
Student Services	1
Trading Room	1

Where would you go to find retention time information?

Ethics	13
Policy Library	4
Listed per Grant	4
eResearch	3
Library	2
Data Management Website	2
HDR handbook	1
Information Management webpage	1
Research Integrity Resource Sheets	1
Digital Solutions	1
National Medical Research Council	1
Aus Responsible Code of Conduct For Research	1

At your current career level, what would be an incentive to reward you to have well-managed research data?

Easier use of Storage systems	12
eLabNotebook	1
Remote access ease	1
Being a data repository for trusted data	1
Unsure	9
No incentive required	59
Being Well organized is its own benefit	22
Being a responsible and ethical researcher	14
Personally motivated	5

More support	19
Supplying a trained data manager	6
More training in data management, methodology and analysis	5
Ease of use of DM protocols	2
Personal Incentive	33
Monetary benefit or Funding	10
More research dedicated time	6
Publication	5
Promotion	4
Recognition from supervisors	3
Award	2
Personal Development Plan points	2
Access to research articles on various platforms	1

15 Appendix I – Survey Results Explorer

Griffith Internal Power BI board

16 Appendix J – Scan of Open and FAIR published data from Griffith

Results of a basic environmental scan on Griffith University-affiliated datasets in repositories undertaken 26/07/2022. Known multi-disciplinary and relevant discipline registries and repositories were searched. Figshare and Zenodo were not counted in the 250+ stated due to difficulty of verifying.

GRO Research Data <https://research-repository.griffith.edu.au/handle/10072/392601>
90 datasets, 78 are open or mediated access.

Figshare <https://figshare.com/> [Didn't include in count due to difficulty of verifying]
Between 55-1000+ datasets

It is very difficult to search by author successfully, some researchers were not necessarily with Griffith at time of data deposit or are now no longer with Griffith. Cannot search on "institution" field.

Searching "Griffith University" as a keyword search identifies 1,114 results.

The best result was using :funding: "Griffith University" with 55 results . Some of these were joint projects with other universities. There were also errors in the results I don't think the phrase search works correctly.

Dryad <https://datadryad.org/>

90 datasets attributed to authors from Griffith University (may not be current)

Could browse by institution, but not search by and phrase search did not work properly.

https://datadryad.org/search?f%5Bdryad_author_affiliation_name_sm%5D%5B%5D=Griffith+University

Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/> [Didn't include in count due to difficulty of verifying]
390 datasets however difficult to confirm, it appears that Griffith University is located in a metadata field which is not displayed publicly. I have identified a number of Griffith researchers in the results.
<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=%22griffith%20university%22>

Australian Data Archive (ADA) <https://ada.edu.au/>
32 datasets, all but 5 associated with Prosecution Project <https://prosecutionproject.griffith.edu.au/>

Research Data Australia registry <https://researchdata.edu.au/>
36 records associated with Griffith including links to national repositories to which Griffith researchers have submitted data:

- Australian National Corpus <https://ns.ausnc.org.au/corpora/gcsause>
- IMOS Catalogue
<https://metadata.imas.utas.edu.au/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/e0f96ebf-b42a-4b0f-876c-2af087bc02dc>
- AURIN: <https://data.aurin.org.au/dataset/gu-urp-gu-urp-vampire-cdd-2001-cd>
- dead links to old Griffith repository (Equella) datasets.
- [The Open River Catalogue](#) dead link

TERN & TERN Supersites Data portals <https://supersites.tern.org.au/knb/>
Holds a number of Griffith related datasets but need to check each individually to confirm accuracy of attribution.
<https://portal.tern.org.au/gold-coast-broadwater-mapping-200508/19475>

AODN (Open Access to Ocean Data) <https://portal.aodn.org.au/search>
4 Griffith related or contributed to datasets

EcoCommons <https://www.ecocommons.org.au/>
Unable to identify how many datasets because of lack of access.

TerraNova - The Australian Climate Change Adaptation Information Hub
1 database plus other objects including reports. There may be other Griffith affiliated datasets as this is a Griffith supported platform. [Northern Australian Aquatic Assets Geodatabase v2.0](#)

Glygen <https://glygen.org/>
Griffith University will be a data contributor, but I am unable to search it. Matthew Campbell from the Institute for Glycomics is a member of the Tool Development and Data Integration team.

Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)

<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu.au>

2 datasets

- <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/ICPSR/studies/20201>
- <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/ICPSR/studies/37935>

For Creative Arts, there is archival material that has been submitted to State Library of Queensland, QLD State Archives and other organisations, searchable via the catalogues.

Rock Art Database <https://rockartdatabase.com/>

6 Griffith University records